

THE CONTRASTⁱ AND THE FUNCTION OF THE GENDER ALBANIAN TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

In Albanian and English language we have three kinds of gender: *masculine*, *feminine* and *neuter*. In Albanian language the concept for gender, is: “Gjinia është një nga kategoritë gramatikore më karakteristike për emrat në gjuhën shqipe. Nga natyra e saj, ajo dallohet nga kategoritë e tjera të emrit, nga numri, rasa dhe nga kategoritë e shquarsisë dhe të pashquarsisë, sepse i kundërvihet mashkullore-femërore dhe asnjësore...”ⁱⁱ. This Albanian citation is possible to be the similar and within English language e.g: “a grouping of nouns and pronouns into classes’ masculine, feminine and neuter”ⁱⁱⁱ or “gender differs from the grammatical categories, case, and definiteness, in being a lexical as well as inflection category of the noun. The gender to which a give word belongs is a property of that particular word independent of context”^{iv}. The contrast of gender between two languages are e.g: **the cases** (five in Albanian with different endings and two in English), definite and indefinite nouns (the masculine nouns for Albanian language has some engings: -i, -it, -in, -it, -u, -un, -ut, for *feminine* -e, -a, -ja, -je, -s, -së, -në, or for neuter

ⁱ A S Hornby, Christina Ruse, **Oxford Student’s Dictionary of Current English**, New York, Oxford, 1988, p.136 -137: The meaning of the word contrast in this dictionary is: contrast /kontrast/ n 1 nu the act of contrasting people, things: Contrast may make something appear more beautiful than it is when seen alone. 2 nc, nu (something showing) a difference clearly seen when unlike things are put together: the contrast between the two brothers is remarkable. In contrast (to you), I shall agree to the proposal. Harry’s marks were poor but Tom’s were excellent by contrast.

Contrast /kontrast/ v 1 vt to compare (two or more people, things, ideas etc) so that differences are made clear: She contrasted the features of a comedy with those of a tragedy. 2. Vi to show a difference when compared: His poor abilities contrast badly with his brother’s talent.

ⁱⁱ Fatmir Agallari, **Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe**, Tiranë, 2002, p.88.

ⁱⁱⁱ A S Hornby, Christina Ruse, **Oxford student’s dictionary of current English**, New York, 2001, p. 263.

^{iv} Leonard Newmark, **Standard Albanian grammar for students**, California, 1982, p.131.

nouns with *-i*, *-it* and for indefinite nouns is: /një/. The definite nouns of English language has the article /the/ and for indefinite /a, an/ than in Albanina some endings. The definite nouns e.g: (masculine noun) *mali* – **the** mountain, *libër-i* – **the** book, *kompjuter -i* – **the** computer; *mësues -i* – **the** teacher; *motër* – sister, *motra* – **the** sister (...).

Keywords: contrast, gender, masculine, feminine and neuter, noun, adjective, pronoun, case, definite, indefinite, singular, plural

Introduction

The gender^v can share in both of (languages) numbers in singular and plural. All of the nouns in masculine, feminine can end with consonant or vowel. “Gender differs from the grammatical categories, case, and definiteness, in being a lexical as well as an inflectional category of noun (...). “The genders of nouns in Albanian are marked by:

1. the case endings of the indefinite and definite singular forms;
2. the form of adjective and other determining words like the pronouns *ky* “this (m.)”, *kjo* “this (f.)”, *ai* “he”, *ajo* “she”, *im* “my (m.)”, *ime* “my (f.)” etc.
3. the terminal sounds of the stem”^{vi}.

The first contrast of gender between two languages are the cases, the second are definite and indefinite, the third are articles, the fourth are prefix and suffix, the fifth are endings etc. Albanian language has five cases: “emërore – nominative, gjinore – genitive, dhanore – dative, kallëzore – accusative, and rrjedhore – ablative”^{vii} and for definite and indefinite have some endings than in English language has two cases: the unmarked COMMON case and the marked GENETIVE”. The latter is sometimes called the possessive^{viii}.

The definite and indefinite nouns (in singular and plural) in Albanian language has some different endings for masculine, *feminine* and *neuter* e.g. for masculine: *-i*, *-it*, *-in*, *-it*, *-u*, *-un*, *-ut*, for *feminine* *-e*, *-a*, *-ja*, *-je*, *-s*, *-së*, *-në*, or for neuter nouns with *-i*, *-it* etc. It is the full contrast between Albanian and English because in English the definite nouns for singular usually has article “the” but Albanian language usually has the endings (as in table A1, A2, A3) e.g.

^v A S Hornby, Christina Ruse, **Oxford Student’s Dictionary of Current English**, New York, Oxford, 1988, p. 263 is:

A grouping of nouns and pronouns into classes (masculine, feminine and neuter).

^{vi} Ibidem, p. 131.

^{vii} Leonard Newmark, **Standard Albanian grammar for students**, California, 1982, p.134.

^{viii} Sidney Greenbaum, Randolph Quirk, **A student’s grammar of the English language**, London, 1997, p. 102.

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i pashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular - njëjës	Indefinite –i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural – shumës
Nominative	libër - book	libri ^{ix} – the book	libra- boks	librat- the books
Genitive	i libri – of th book	i librit-of the book	i librave-of books	i librave-of the books
Dative	libri – the book	librit- the book	librave – books	librave –the books
Accusative	libër – book	librin- the book	libra- books	librat-the books
Ablative	libri – the book	librit- the book	librash- books	librave-the books

Table A1: Masculine noun

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i pashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular njëjës	Indefinite –i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural – shumës
Nominative	mik-friend	miku-the friend	miq-friends	miqtë-the friends
Genitive	i miku-of the friend	i mikut-of the friend	i miqve-of friends	i miqve-of the friends
Dative	miku-the friend	mikut-the friend	miqve- friends	miqve-the friends
Accusative	mik-friend	mikun- the friend	miqve-friends	miqtë-the friends
Ablative	miku – the friend	mikut –the friend	miqsh- friends	miqve-the friends

Table A2: Masculine noun

The case Rasa	Indefinite –i ashqar singular – njëjës	Definite – e shqar singular - njëjës	Indefinite – i pashqar plural – shumës	Definite – e shqar plural - shumës
Nominative	Motër - sister	motra - the sister	motra – sisters	motrat - the sisters
Genitive	i motre - of sister	i motrës - of the sister	i motrave - of sisters	i motrave - of the sisters
Dative	motre – sister	motrës - the sister	motrave - sisters	Motrave - the sisters
Accusative	motër – sister	motrën - the sister	motra – sisters	Motrat - the sisters
Ablative	motre – sister	motrës - the sister	motrash – sisters	Motrave - the sisters

Table A2: Feminine noun

In the table A1 the first declension has some similarities, differences, contrasts between Albanian and English language. The noun /libër - book/ in the nominative case

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [European Journal of English Language Teaching](http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/295/742), <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/295/742>

has the contrast because in Albanian it has the ending *-i*, for singular and */-a, -at/* for plural, than in English has the definite article */the^x/* and in plural has ending */-s/*.

The possessive case, in Albanian language can be realized with the article (*masculine, feminine and neuter*) **i** (m), **e** (f), **të** (n) and **së** (f) or with definite endings **-i, -it, -in, -ve** (m), or **-u, -ut, -un** (m), but in **English** this case is used with the article **/the/** for definite nouns (m, f, n), so between two languages it is the contrast because it has two forms of possessive and usually used after the noun e.g. *Mary's book, Time's house, students', worker's, children's, women's, This is Arta's jacket, This is my mother's jacket. This is the dog's food.* If a plural noun does not end in */s/*, add *'s*. *women's, men's, children's^{xi}* etc. This phenomenon of grammar is the contrast between two languages.

If the noun in plural ending with the consonant and in the common case it in the possessive gets just apostrophe (*'s*), (*'*) *boys', students', books', it's* another contrast. The noun in singular can end with the consonant and in the common cases it in the possessive gets apostrophe or apostrophe and *-s* e.g. **today's, last week's, a mother's, two mothers, 's boss', son-in-law's, sister-in-law's, man's, Richard's, cat's, dog's. The boy's book is on the table. The wife's house is near here. If the singular nouns in -s, there are two possible forms, the first apostrophe^{xii} and -s how my wife's or only an apostrophe Thomas' teacher** etc. If the compound words or phrasal it has this function of possessive: **mother-in-law, get add's mother-in-law's, son-in-law's, sister-in-law's.** However, both of languages have a contrast for this phenomenon of grammar, Albanian has the article **i, e, të, së** and English has */, 's/*. The Albanian language (gender m, f, n) has the **dative, accusative and ablative** that aren't **exist** in English e.g. *Tregoi babait. Iu afrova Teuta.* The genitive case of these forms are mainly used for a variety of determining expressed in English by prepositional phrases introduced by **of**, or by the so-called possessive **-s**, or by nouns used as adjective. They often follow a referent noun or pronoun, explicit or implicit in the sentence and indicate:

- a. the affiliation with or ownership of the referent: **libri i bibliotekës – the library book', oborri i shkollës – the school yard'**.
- b. *Lulet e majit - The May flowers'. Hapja e dritareve – the opening of the windows'. Shumica e studentëve – the majority of students'.* A noun in the genitive case modifying another noun must either be definite or be indefinite and

^x This definite article usually use before the noun. Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, The contrast of Direct object between Albanian and English Language, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, <http://imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/view/1320/1270>

^{xi} Shkelqim Millaku, The genitive, Anglisticum, <http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1218>

phrase modifying mother is My aunt's boyfriend, and the genitive phrase modifying boyfriend is my aunt. The genitive modifying aunt is the determiner my. Here we have structure embedded within structure.

My aunt's boyfriend's mother's car.

Genitive of gender in English and Albanian often has internal grammatical structure. With the exaction of genitive determiners, genitive are noun phrases and can contain its own determiner, just like any other noun phrases. In a phrases: **This boy's father**, this modifies boy not father, the genitive construction modifying father is actually the phrase this boy's. When the nominalized clause is intransitive and thus lacks a direct object, the subject may occupy either the pre-nominal or post-nominal genitive position. Thus consider:

The city's growth.

The growth of the city.

Paula's escape to Malta.

The escape of Paul to Malta.^{xv}

The genitive (word) can be in the sentence at the beginning, middle or in the end. The tree or diagram of the simple sentence can follow the genitive that is in the beginning of sentence:

The students' hands the teacher their quizzes^{xvi}

^{xv} T. Givon. (1996). **English grammar**. Philadelphia, p. 292.

^{xvi} Shkelqim Millaku, *Anglisticum Journal (IJLLIS)*, Volume: 4 | Issue: 4 April 2015 |

<http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/viewFile/156/137>,

<http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1218>

^{xvii} Shkelqim Millaku, *The contrast of Direct object between Albanian and English Language*, *IJIR*,

<http://imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/view/1320>

^{xviii} Shkelqim Millaku, *The direct object*, *Anglisticum*,

<http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

^{xix} Max Morenberg. (2002). **Doing Grammar**. New York, p. 43.

This diagram of the sentence “**The students’** hands **the teacher their quizzes**” the genitive is the subject “the students’” and it is not correct with the indirect object, because it needs to be one tree by noun phrase and by it to generate direct or indirect object.

A. The masculine nouns

The masculine nouns on Albanian language usually can end with the consonant or vowel e.g. **student, hotel, ballkon, film, tren, lis, mal, gur, djalë, burrë** etc.,

All nouns that end with consonant -r, -ll, -l precedent by -ë or -u e.g. **gur – “stone”, mal – “mountain”, gëzim – “joy”**.

All the nouns that ends in a stressed vowel like with: **dru – “wood”, zë – “voice”, zëri – “the sound”**.

-ë: djalë “boy”, burrë – “man”, djathë – “the cheese”, lumë – “river”, Kolë, Dedë etc.

-i: ulli, flori, qiri, shiri etc.

-e: pe, dre, dhe etc.

-u: dru, kërceu, hu etc.

-a: pasha, baba, aga etc.

-ua: thua, përrua, krua (njeri-u, veri-u, baba-i, atdhe-u, dru - druri, sy - syri, zë - zëri) etc.

English language has the same structure of masculine, it can end in the stressed with consonant or vowel e.g. father, uncle, brother, nephew, duke, God, hero, friend, student (common), boyfriend, student etc. In both of languages the nouns are used in singular or plural. In Albanian language and English the most common methods of plural formation in by adding a plural suffix to the singular form. The nouns usually ending with consonant in the indefinite form or in definite with /-i, -u/ e.g. **emër-i, gur-i, qytet-i, mik-u, shok-u, krua-kroi, përrua-përroi, mure – walls, lisa – oaks, burra – men, desh – rams, net – nights, miq – friends, zogj – birds, brigje – hills, atë – fathers** etc.

The definite nouns in English language usually make with article /the/ and it is contrast with Albanian because the definite nouns in Albanian are usually with the suffix e.g. **djalë – djali – boy - the boy, libër – libri – book – the book^{xx}**.

The definite nouns between Albanian and English are the full contrast because English has /the/ as an article that can show before the noun, so in Albanian it has **-i, -u, -a, -të**, that have the function as a suffixes.

Both of languages it can make the plural nouns. It can build with suffixes. The formation of the plural of masculine nouns is quite complex and usually can formation

^{xx} Shkelqim Millaku, **Anglisticum**, Volume 4, issue 4, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-1878 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179

with suffixation. The Albanian language has a lot of suffixes that are productive for too creative the new plural nouns e.g.

The plural is also formed with *-e*. With this suffixes usually can creative or found the abstract nouns. All the nouns that ending with suffix *-im*, as well as borrowed words that end in *-ion, -um*, take *-e*, in the plural e.g. *aksione – aksions, leksione – lectures, albume – albums, stadiume – stadiums, simpoziume – symposiums, vendime – decisions, mendime – thoughts, studim-e, qytet-e – cities, , seminar-e, hotel-e, kat-e – floors, document-e – documents, tunel-e – tunnels, kanal-e – canals, shtete – states, katunde – villages, vende – place, elemente – elements, ideale – ideals, hotele – hotels, tunele – tunnels, zakone – customs, motive – motives, sheshe – fields* etc.

The plural is also formed with *-a* e.g. *telefon-a, gjel-a, krimb-a, dema – bulls’, trupa – bodies, pëllumba – pigeons’, topa – balls* etc.

The plural is also formed with *-ë* e.g. *shok-ë, anëtar-ë, doktor-ë, dhëmbë, lek-ë, artist-ë, arsimtar-ë – educators, formular-ë – forms, artist-ë – artists, punëtor-ë – worker, studentë – students, drur-ë – trees, fshatar-ë – villagers, beqarë – bachelors, berberë – berbers, doctorë – doctorës, policë – policemen* etc. “Me sy të mbyllur doktor Gurametoja priste vendimin.”^{xxi}

-a: gjel-a, telefona, derra, dema – bulls, qingja – lambs, tipa – types, trupa – bodies, motora – motors, trëndafila – roses, rripa – slopes, trupa – bodies, bilbila – whistles, emra – names, numra – numbers etc.

-e: qytet-e, hotel-e, seminar-e, pus-e, vende – place’, kate – floors’, palate – apartments’, festivale – festivals’, male – mountains’, hotele – hotels’, sheshe – fields’, motive – motives’.

-nj: bari-nj, kushëri-nj, ari-nj, gjuhnjë – knees’, thonj – fingernails’, langonj – hounds’ etc.

-enj: lumë –lumenj – rivers’, lëmë-lëmenj, përrua- përrenje – brooks’, budallenj – fools’, maskarenj – knaves etc.

-inj: shkëmb-shkëmbinj – rocks, drapërinj – sickles, gishtërinj – snakes, shkop-shokpinj, zotër-zotrinj, ari-nj, gju-nj, hero-nj etc.

-ër: prindër – parents, vëllezër – brothers, robber – captives, mbretër – kings, nipër – nephews etc.

The plural of some nouns is marked only by a change in the stem vowel, usually from *a* to *e*, or sometimes opposite of them e.g. *-a/e: dash (ram)-desh, çjap (billy)-çjep, ka (ox) – qe, gardh (fence) – gjerdhe* etc.

^{xxi} Ismail Kadare, *Darkë e gabuar*, Tiranë, 2008, p.50.

There are in Albanian three sub-types of the plural type formed by the politicization of the velar consonant g and k into gj and q e.g. **mik-miq (friends), bujk-bujq – farmer, peshk – peshq – fishes, cak-caqe - limit, bllok – blloqe – block, tog, togje – pile, treg – trgje – market, park – parqe – park, varg – vargje – rangs, zog- zogj, murg-murgj, breg-brigje - hills, shteg – shtigje – pass.**

Both of languages have regular and irregular noun forms for to creative plural. English language has not same form with Albanian because in English we have the suffixes **-s, -es** for to creative the plural nouns **boy - boys, dog - dogs, buse - buses, name – names** or irregular forms **man - men, woman - women, toph – teeth** etc.

The same form in both of languages is: **they have regular and irregular forms; the regular make the forms with suffixes and irregular change the form.**

B. The feminine noun

The Albanian language has a lot of feminine nouns that ending with vowel or consonant and the suffixes is the most usual process of formation plural forms. The most productive suffixes are **-a, -ra** etc. The following nouns form the plural with the suffixes e.g. **fusha – filds, lodra – games, mjegulla – fogs, flutura – butterfly, motra - sisters** etc. The feminine nouns in Albanian language usually can know by the suffixes and the most productive are: **-ë, -e, -i, -a, -o, ël, ër, -eshë, -ë, -ushë, -icë, onjë** etc. for example:

-ë -mollë, nënë, vajzë, rrobë, detyrë, dhomë-a, dorë-a, kokë-a, gjuhë-a etc.

-e: lule, nuse, faqe, fitore etc.

-i: dituri, teori, gjini, fotografi, malësi, bukuri etc.

-a: kinema, kala, para, hua etc.

-o: depo, dado, pallto, kosto, radio etc. or **zemër, vegël, femër, këmbëz, vetulla.**

-ël-, -ër, -e si vegël-a, motër-a, lule-ja, lodhje-ja.

-e, -eshë, -ë, -ushë, -icë, onjë e.g: **gjysh-e, mik-e, ministër-e, doktor-ersh, plakë-ë, zonzë, arushë.**

The English language can build the feminine nouns with root of male so it can get the suffixes **-ess** e.g.

• Masculine	Feminine
• Actor	actress
• Master	mistress
• Heir	heiress
• Lion	lioness
• Poet	poetess etc.

Both of languages have regular and irregular plural form of nouns or in English we have some forms e.g.

/-s, es/; bus - buses, house - houses, prize - prizes, brush - brushes, punch - punches, thing - things, dog - dogs, day - days, boy - boys.

/-y - i/; lady - ladies, story - stories, army - armies, country - countries, fly - flies.

/-y/; day-days, play-plays, tray-trays, key-keys, boy-boys, toy-toys.

/-s/; truth - truths, wearth - wearths, mouth-mouths, path-paths.

Irregular plural nouns: **zero - zeroes or zeros, commando - commandoes or commandos, man - men, woman - women, mouse - mice, life-lives, wolf-wolves, knife - knives, half-halves, wife-wives** etc.

In Albanian language the plural of feminine nouns can make with suffixes **-a, -ra** etc. for example: **banka, vera kashtëra, nënë, (ca) nëna, një fushë (ca) fusha, një bankë (ca) banka, ditët, rrugët, udhët, derë - duar, derë - dyer, natë netë** etc. In English language are some forms of possibility for to build the plural nouns e.g.

- **-s cat-cats, dog-dogs, day-days.**
- **-y--i: baby-babies, story-stories, lady-ladies.**
- **s, z, c, xh, zh in plural gets suffixes -es; glass - glasses, place - places, bush - bushes, branch - branches** etc.
- **-f, -ves, or -s e.g. leaf - leaves, knife - knives, roof - roofs, shelf - shelves** etc.

The irregular nouns: **woman - women, fisherman - fishermen, child - children, ox - oxen, foot-feet, tooth - teeth, goose - geese, mouse - mice** etc.

C. The neuter nouns

The neuter nouns exist in both of languages. In Albanian language we have e.g. kryet, të ecurit, të menduarit, se foluri, brumë, drithë, dyllë, mish, miell (from adjective) të zitë, të bardhtë, të ftohtë (from verb) të folurit, të qeshurit etc. **This is same in English e.g. book, house, desk, tree, wall, a street, a flower, a table, a fork, a pen, a spoon, love** etc.

We have in both of languages a lot of nouns that are ambiguous for example in Albanian: **male, malet tona, qytete tona, qytete të mëdha, vende malore, vendim i drejtë, djepi, ligji, busti, naftë, program, loti, thekër** etc.

In English it is the same for example: **friend, girlfriend or boyfriend, child, partner, writer, professor, teacher, student, speaker, pupil, person** etc.

The animal nouns e.g. **bull - cow, drake - duck, horse - mare, dog - bitch** etc.

The plural form of the neuter noun **krey - head, chief, krerë - heads, or krerë bagëtish - heads of cattle** it is change **ye - e** and suffix **-rë**.

Personal dual gender is a large including, for example, the following: **artist, fool, musician, speaker, student, teacher, writer, professor, person, parent, neighbor, friend, doctor, cook** etc.

D. The number of nouns

In both of languages the noun has two numbers: singular and plural. In English language we can see in the following some forms of singular and plural nouns;

- | | | | |
|---------------|---------------------------|------------|----------------------------|
| • One book | two books ^{xxii} | one watch | two watches |
| • One boy | two boys | one church | two churches |
| • One problem | two problems | one house | two house |
| • One thing | two things | one bus | two buses |
| • One shop | two shops | one dish | two dishes |
| • One name | two names | one glass | two glasses |
| • One flower | two flowers | one box | two boxes ^{xxiii} |

The English and Albanian this form is possible to be the same, for example: **një dyqan, two shops - dy dyqane, një emër - one name - two names** etc.

In Albanian and English we have some nouns that can have the same structure only in singular e.g. abstract nouns: **dashuri - dashuria, guxim - guximi, uri - uria, Kos - kosi, benzinë - benzina, qumësht - qumështi, the month, year, nouns: janari, shkurti, marsi, January, April, June, October etc. matematikë, histori, kimi, fizikë, Chemist, Ardita, Xhoni, Teuta, London, Parisi, veri, jug, lindje, perëndim, North, West, East, South** etc.

In Albanian and English we have some nouns that can use only in plural, for example: **makarona - makaronat (macaroni), krunde - krunde (bran), dhentë - sheep, viset - places, syze - syzet, gërshtët - gërshtët, miellra - miellrat, vajra - vajrat, miell, krunde, kokrrat, pantallonat, syzat, plakat, lajkat, ethet, pllakat, Alpe, Mrize, Kodër, shpatet, viset, lugjet** etc. In English we have some nouns that are with same structure with singular:

- | • Singular | Plural | • Singular | Plural |
|------------|--------|------------|---------|
| • Deer | deer | • // | goods |
| • Fish | fish | • // | tropics |
| • Sheep | sheep | • // | jeans |
| • Series | series | • // | shorts |
| | | • // | glasses |

“The noun **sheep, deer, cod** etc., that are countable nouns do not have different between singular or plural e.g.

This **sheep** has just had a lamb

These **sheep** have just had lambs”.^{xxiv}

^{xxii} Shkelqim Millaku, The noun phrase, Anglisticum,

<http://aassee.eu/anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/1254>

^{xxiii} Shukrane Gërmizaj, **A comprehensives handbook of English grammar**, Prishtina, 2004, p.149.

^{xxiv} Sideny Greenbaun (...), **A student’s grammar of the English language**, London, England, 1990, p.95.

The number of nouns, the plural usually make with suffixes –es. –s for example: **Cat - cats, map - maps, boy - boys, girl - girls, case - cases, house – houses** etc. By the examples we can consider we have two forms, singular and plural. It is same with both of languages.

E. The gender of countable and uncountable nouns

In Albanian and English language we have countable and uncountable nouns. The countable nouns are all the nouns e.g. **Prishtina, Shkupi, Drini, Morava, libër, shkollë, mësues, mielli, uji, plakat, lajkat, ethet** etc, or in English: *“I bought some chairs, tables, and desks. In other words, I bought some furniture”*.^{xxv}

Nouns can be broadly into a small number of classes which have meaning and grammatical behavior. There is an important distinct common and proper nouns. Common nouns can be countable and uncountable. Countable nouns refer to entities which can be counted, they are singular and plural forms (**a cow, two cows**) etc.). Both in the singular and plural there is a contrast between definite and indefinite forms (**a cow, two cows, the cows**).

Countable nouns have both singular and plural forms, referring to one or more than one entity, respectively.

Uncountable nouns refer to entities which cannot be counted and uncounted for number. Though they do not combine with the indefinite article, the contrast between an indefinite and definite form (e.g. milk, the milk) ...^{xxvi}

Countable nouns are same in both of language: We can find large number of countable nouns for example:

Person	businessman^{xxvii}, journalist, yachtsman,
Concrete objects	boat, present, vacuum cleaner,
Actions	event, move, race,
Other abstractions	contribution, result, rule.

It needs to be stressed again that countability is not a simple reflection of things observed in the external world. For example, even a countable noun such as thing is used not only with reference to discrete concrete objects, but also to abstractions which do not so obviously or naturally come as distinct entities see the use of these things in the following example: I have only got it confirmed, but these things take time.

^{xxv} Batty Schramper Azar, **English grammar**, Washington, 2006, p.107.

^{xxvi} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoken and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.245.

^{xxvii} Shkelqim Millaku, The compound nouns between English and Albanian, EJES,

<http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/216>

In Albanian language we find plurals noun for example: **karrikë - karrika, libër - libra, shtëpi - shtëpa** etj. So, a countable noun in English has plurals and can be used **a/an. A chair - chairs, a book - books, a house – houses** etc.

F. The uncountable nouns

Uncountable nouns have plurals (Albanian and English, too), and cannot normally be used with e.g. **air, water, English, weather**.

She speaks good English. (Not. She speaks good English).

Ajo e flet mirë anglishtne. (Jo. Ajo e flet një anglishte mirë).

In English the article *a, an* can use for to make the noun in singular and */a/* used before the noun that begin with consonant and *an* used before the words that begin with vowel.

She speaks good English.

It's terrible weather. (Not. a terrible weather).

In English and Albanian we have some nouns that are countable and uncountable e.g.

I'll have a cup of **coffee**, please. Did you remember to buy **coffee**?

We use common nouns to categorize or label people and things. They are countable and uncountable. We can use countable common nouns in the singular, with *a/an* and *each*, or in the plural, with *number* and *many*. Do you have a black **pen** or a **pencil**?

We usually use uncountable common nouns when we talk about as abstract concept, or activity, a substance or a material. Uncountable nouns are not used with *a/an* or in the plural. We can use uncountable nouns with no article (*a*) and *much* (*b*).

a. Her poem is about flying, freedom and bad luck. (not. a bad luck).

b. They have food clothing, but they don't have much water. (not waters).

"Countable nouns can be singular or plural and are normally used to refer to people, creatures and objects, or actions and events, which can be thought of as separate individual things e.g. actor, bird, car, man, party, problem est."^{xxviii}

Uncountable nouns are used with singular verbs, but not to refer to individual things. They are not typically used with *a/an*. We use uncountable nouns to talk about substance and materials, abstracts ideas, qualities and states or activities e.g. chess, tennis, work, education, freedom, love, meat, petrol, rice etc.

The examples **ice, love, time arrival, contact, news, time feedback, theory, importance** are types of meaning which can be countable and uncountable nouns: substances (*air, ice*), emotional and other (*news, receivership, contact*); qualities

^{xxviii} George Yule, **Oxford practice grammar**, Oxford, 2008, p. 74.

(importance), events (arrival). Many nouns which are basically uncountable also have countable with difference meaning. We have some examples: time (denoting a particular occasion or a period in history), air (denoting a tune or a type of appearance or manner).

“The things we can count are called count nouns. The things we can not are called non count nouns. A non count noun does not have a plural form and we can not put a number in front of it. We never use **a/an** with non count nouns. Count nouns example: **a book - books, one book - two books, some books, a lot of books, many books, a few books or non count nouns singular: sugar, same sugar, a lot of sugar, much sugar, a little sugar.**^{xxix}

The use of a noun as countable or uncountable is lexically restricted difference in meaning varies to a large extent with the individual noun. The short form of countable is C and for uncountable is U.

Both can be C/U nouns, but in the contest we can know different of meaning. For example:

- a. Six **teas** please. (C)
- b. It was in fact impossible to be strenuously diligent after one of Mrs Sutton’s **teas**. (C)
- c. Plant beverage include **tea, coffee, wine, ...**and sweet beverage (U)
- d. We learned to eat brown **rice** and yogurt and to tolerate kasha and add-tasting teas.

The countable instances of tea are used in the sentence “a cup of tea’ /a/ “a type of tea’ and “a small meal usually served in the afternoon with a cup of tea” b. The uses illustrated in /a and d/ are often found with other basically uncountable nouns.

Countable and uncountable nouns we have and abstract nouns, for example **education, freedom**, etc.

G. Plural uncountable nouns

Although it may seem to be a contradiction, there are plural uncountable. These are morphologically plural nouns which do not vary for number and do not combine with numerals:

She wears those jigsaw-type **clothes, trousers** usually.

Unite nouns are in a way the opposite of collective nouns: rather than provide a collective reference for separate entities, they make it possible to split up an undifferentiated mass and refer to separate instances of a phenomenon. Both types of noun provide alternative ways of viewing

^{xxix} Kathryn Church, **American English workbook**, Tirana, 2002, p.25.

and referring, collective nouns with respect to countable and until nouns with respect to uncountable^{xxx}.

With bit of and piece of are the most productive, each combining with well over 100 different collocates.

Unit noun	Selected collocates
Act of	adultery, kindness, folly^{xxxi},
Bit of	beef, cake, cheese, sugar, paper,
Chip of	glass, ice, paint,
Chunk of	chocolate, meat, gold, data,
Game of	cards, chess, golf, tennis,
Grain of	corn, dust, salt, sand,
Item of	clothing, information, equipment,
Loaf of	bread,
Lump of	clay, soil, butter, fat,
Piece of	cake, chicken, wood,
Pair of	clippers, glasses, plants,
Slice of	pie, ham, bread etc.

Here are some groups of nouns:

1. Countable nouns with singular (and plural) in –is, analysis, analyses, crossroads, series.
2. Other nouns with singular and plural the same: **trout, deer, fish, salmon.**
3. Nouns that have a plural without –s after a number hundred (two hundred) million (two million)...
4. Nouns with singular in –f (e), plural in –ves, **calf - calves, wife - wives, knife - knives, self - selves.**
5. Nouns with irregular plurals: **man - men, woman - women, child - children, foot - feet.**
6. Uncountable singular nouns ending in –s (normally no plural) **billiards, economics, politics, gymnastics.**
7. Plural nouns with no singular e.g. **arms, clothes, people, trousers, congratulations** etc.
8. To form the plural nouns, add –s, **table - tables, room - rooms, desk - desks,** etc.
9. If the noun ends s, sh, ch, x, or z add es, **glass - glasses, dish - dishes, church - churches, box - boxes** etc.

^{xxx} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoken and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.250

^{xxxi} Shkelqim Millaku, THE FUNCTION OF NOUN PHRASES BETWEEN ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH, WEI, 2016, <http://www.westeastinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Shkelqim-Millaku.pdf>

10. If the noun ends in a /y/ preceded by a vowel (a, e, i, o, u) only add /s/, **day-s, guy-s, key-s** etc.
11. If the noun ends in on/o/ preceded by a consonant, add -es. **Potato - potatoes, hero - heroes, tomato - tomatoes, radios, zoo - zoos.**
12. If the noun is a compound, make the noun plural, not the modifier: **mother-in-low --- mothers-in-low, piece of cake - pieces of cake.**
13. If the number, litter, or sing is considered as a word, add 's. **1900's, (1900), 10-10'së ABC-ABC's.**
14. Some nouns are same in the singular and plural, **fish - fish, deer - deer, sheep - sheep.**
15. Some nouns are always plural: **mathematics, pants, cloths** etc.

Plural and uncountable nouns with and without /the/ (**flowers**) **the flowers, music- the music.**

1. We do not use /the/ before a noun when we mean something in general: I love flowers (not, the flowers). I prefer classical music to pop music. (Not, the classical music....)^{xxxii}.

2. We say /the/ ... when the mean something in particular. I like your garden. The flowers are beautiful. All the students in the class like their teacher.

3. We do not usually say with the names of countries, cities, and village. Franca not the France, Europe not the Europe, or New York, Prishtina, Paris etc.

We can say with /the/ names which include works like: **republic, kingdom, states. The United Kingdom, the United States of America, the Republic of...**

Regions: the north of England, the south of Spain, etc.

Regular count nouns:

Singular	Plural
Lemon	Lemons
Song	Songs
Egg	Eggs
List	Lists
Cake	Cakes
Orange	Oranges
Idea	Ideas
Glass	Glasses
Dish	Dishes
Sandwich	Sandwiches
Box	Boxes

^{xxxii} Raymond Murphy, **English grammar in use**, Cambridge, 1992, p. 148.

H. Irregular count nouns:

Man	Men
Woman	Women
Child	Children
Person	People
Foot	Feet
Tooth	Teeth
Mouse	Mice

“Some words (English) borrowed from Latin and Greek keep their foreign plural, or their maybe alternation with regular plural forms.

Latin nouns ending –us

Alumnus - alumni

Calculus - calculi

Terminus - termini

Latin nouns ending in –um

Aquarium - aquaria

Curriculum - curricula

Millennium - millennia”

Index - indices.^{xxxiii}

Greek nouns ending in-is:

Axis – axes, crisis - crises, diagnosis - diagnoses.

The build of nouns in singular and plural, masculine, feminine and neuter, countable or uncountable are augmented for both of languages for reports that have the same or different between two languages.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is to point out of similarities, differences, contrasts or generation of gender between Albanian and English language by comparing different (function) parts of speech. The first contrast of gender between two languages are the cases (page 2), the second are definite and indefinite (page 4), the third are articles, the fourth are prefix and suffix, the fifth are endings etc. In page three has some tables (A1, 2, 3) it is the first declension that has some similarities, differences, contrasts between Albanian and English language. The full contrast between two language was seen at the possessive case, in Albanian language can be realize with the article (for *masculine*,

^{xxxiii} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoken and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.286

feminine and *neuter*) **i** (m), **e** (f), **të** (n) and **së** (f) or with definite endings **-i, it, -in, -ve** (m), or **-u, -ut, -un** (m), but in **English** this case used with the article **/the/** for definite nouns (m, f, n), so between two languages it is the contrast because it has two forms of possessive and usually used after the noun e.g. *Mary's book, Time's house, students', worker's, children's, women's, This is Arta's jacket, This is my mother's jacket. This is the dog's food.* If a plural noun does not end in /s/, add 's. *women's, men's, children's* etc. This phenomenon of grammar is the morphology contrast between two languages and in the future we will see the function (syntax) of the gender in the sentence.

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